

Intellectual Output 2 (O2)

Output title:

Educational Content and support

Output description:

Development of educational content in multi-formats and modalities to ensure training in basic, intermediate and advanced level e-skills: Basic level- 1) create an e-mail account; 2) Login and logout with security; 3) Text writing; 4) to do an image research; 5) Send and receive an email message 6) to share contents with security using web cloud storage platforms. Intermediate level – 1) produce and publish a digital dynamic online presentation; 2) create, edit and share a video; 3) moderate and manage chat rooms and discussion forums; 4) Administrate a videoconference. Advanced level – Create and publish a website using web 2.0 web development tools (provide recognition and certification for this training).

Expected Results:

Tangible - e-modules produced, 1 Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), ebooks;
Intangible - increased experience in e-modules and MOOC creation.

Development of activities and results obtained:

This intellectual output was divided into four activities, three for each contents format and the fourth to the digital tool for the contents.

Each educational content was produced for all the formats mentioned in the project activities (O2-A1 - e-modules; O2-A2 - MOOC; O2-A3 - e-book).

- O2-A1 – Regarding the e-modules they can be seen at <http://eraizes.ipsantarem.pt/moodle/course/view.php?id=521>
- O2-A2 – Concerning the MOOC the contents are already on the developed website in all partners' languages:
Portuguese – <http://cctic.e.se.ipsantarem.pt/digital4all/>
English – http://cctic.e.se.ipsantarem.pt/digital4all/en_GB/home-2/
Italian – http://cctic.e.se.ipsantarem.pt/digital4all/it_IT/home-it/
German – http://cctic.e.se.ipsantarem.pt/digital4all/de_DE/home-de/

The user doesn't have to know all the URL for the different languages since they have flag icons on the website to choose their own language at the time.

Also and **added value** to the project is the possibility to due the course in an intercomprehension, meaning that the learner can choose to attend some modules for in the native language (e.g. Portuguese) and others in a foreign language (e.g. English).

- O2-A3 Regarding the ebook it was also published in all languages of the partnership and can be accessed from the website mentioned before. Anyway here are the direct URLs to each ebook:
Portuguese – <http://pt.calameo.com/read/0042163423d0c3b35c38c>
English – <http://pt.calameo.com/read/00421634236ee45c6bfe9>

Italian – <http://pt.calameo.com/read/004216342e740b43f934b>

German – <http://pt.calameo.com/read/0042163423cb523e8f49c>

As described in the O2-A4 a tool for the educational contents was developed. This website was made to address the requirements of the educational contents, using a web 2.0 platform (Wordpress) and by integrating educational modules, such as portfolios, forums, and other. <http://cctic.e.se.ipsantarem.pt/digital4all/> Also, for the e-modules the website connects directly with eRaizes, a platform developed using a Learning Management System (Moodle).

Before using the website with end-users a usability test was performed with students from bachelor degrees of Education and Multimedia Communication. During this test the students were invited to test the platform and to identify errors or design failures. After the test the platform was redeveloped in order to address the identified inaccuracies.

During the development of this intellectual output we had a transnational meeting in Munich, Germany.

This meeting occurred on 7 and 8 of September and aimed to finalise the materials in this IO.

For more information on the meeting please see the agenda

<http://w3.e.se.ipsantarem.pt/uptakeict/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/Uptake ICT 2nd meeting agenda.pdf>

This meeting also launched the activities for the next intellectual output, the paper production.

Extra activities/results (that weren't expected during the application)

In order to accomplish the proposed results, the partnership had **monthly** skype meetings. In these meetings we discussed the methodologies to develop the activities and assessed what was being done by each partner and the next activities expected from each one.

The contents were enriched with a content enrichment platform (Nice reader) developed by the Viatecla partner. This platform allows introducing several multimedia add-ons to a pdf file (e.g., video, audio, assessment tools)

Workshop at Escola Superior de Educação de Santarém in 24th July, 2015 led by the Partner institution Viatecla.

Erasmus+